

INTEGRATION OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND PRODUCTION, PROSPECTS AND CHALLENGES AWAITING SOLUTION

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Abstract: Integration of science, education and production, prospects and problems awaiting solution.

In this article, the role of the environment in the training of personnel, the transfer of scientific ideas and the improvement of the quality of education, the existing problems and their solutions are discussed in this article.

Keywords: science, education, production, integration, innovation, expert, competence, quality, learning process, technology.

Annotatsiya: Fan, ta'lim va ishlab chiqarish integratsiyasi, istiqbol va yechimini kutayotgan muammolar.

Ushbu maqolada ta'lim, fan va ishlab chiqarish integratsiyasini kadrlar tayyorlashdagi, ilmiy g'oyalarni transfer qilish va ta'lim berish sifatini oshirishda muhitni o'rni, mavjud muammolar ularni yechimlari to'g'risida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ilm-fan, ta'lim, ishlab chiqarish, integratsiya, innovatsiya, mutaxassis, kompetensiya, sifat, o'quv jarayoni, texnologiya.

Аннотация: Интеграция науки, образования и производства, перспективы и проблемы, ожидающие решения.

В данной статье обсуждаются условия интеграции образования, науки и производства, трансфера научных идей и повышения качества образования, а также пути решения существующих проблем.

Ключевые слова: наука, образование, производство, интеграция, инновации, эксперт, компетентность, качество, процесс обучения, технологии.

Introduction. No one can deny that it is important to improve the quality of personnel training for the development of the country's economy. The issue of personnel serves as a key in the development of the economy of any country and in increasing its competitiveness. It is possible to achieve the desired goals only through the rapid development of production based on high technologies in the national economy, and the introduction of innovative technologies into the economy.

It is of great importance to ensure the integration of science, education and production in the training of quality personnel.

Currently, we are passing an important stage in the development of education at our university. Educational, research and production activity of students in the educational process is an important part of improving the system of higher education.

We will try to answer the question of what is educational integration and why it is necessary, first of all, educational integration is related to human activity and is a necessary phenomenon aimed at training quality specialists. Also, "integration" is closely related to the concept of "system", because in the process of integration, the system acquires a unique quality - integrity, a set of properties unlike its individual elements. Thus, integration is the process of interaction of various elements that leads to the formation of a new integrated complex.

PQ-916 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 15, 2008 "On additional measures to encourage the application of innovative projects and technologies to production", February 17, 2017 "Organization, management and financing of the

activities of the Academy of Sciences, research and development works" on further improvement measures" No. PQ-2789, dated July 27, 2017 "On measures to further expand the participation of economic sectors and sectors in improving the quality of training of highly educated specialists" No. PQ-3151, Resolutions PQ-4335 of May 23, 2019 "On additional measures for the rapid development of the construction materials industry" and Decree No. PF-5847 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" , as well as the relevant clauses of the Decision PQ-416 of November 8, 2022 "On measures to further improve the personnel training system in the field of architecture and construction", the legal and regulatory frameworks defining the "prospects of the integration of science, education and production" in our country are defined.

In today's modern world, the security and independence of states is inseparable from their level of technological development. The role and importance of each country in the world economy directly depends on its possession of high technologies. The level of development of high technologies, in turn, depends on the country's economic situation and scientific-production potential.

The transition of the economy of developing countries to the path of technological development requires new approaches to the training of highly qualified personnel in technical engineering fields.

The rapid development of science and technology, the replacement of some technologies with new and better ones, and the strengthening of innovative

processes in the production sector create the need for continuous improvement of new knowledge and skills in engineers being trained in higher education institutions.

The uniqueness of many universities in the world is that their main functions are the integration of education, science and production, in addition to the training of specialists. This factor, in theory, creates opportunities for scientists to realize their ideas in the form of finished products, for students to receive better education, and for universities to see income from promising, high-tech venture investments.

The quality level of the graduates of higher educational institutions in the technical direction - the quality of the educational (training) program;

- the quality of personnel and scientific potential involved in the educational process;
- the quality of students (including applicants entering a higher education institution);
- to the quality of educational process tools (material, technical, experimental base);

Everyone knows that it depends on a number of factors, such as educational and methodological support. At the same time, it is necessary to look for a number of unused opportunities in the current era of rapid development.

The main idea of the modern development of the theory and practice of quality management of technical engineering education is that in order not to lag behind advanced technologies, it is necessary to abandon some unjustified traditional approaches to education.

Engineering and technical education does not limit quality management only to assessment and control, but also involves the creation of additional conditions that ensure this quality more fully. One of the components of this integrity is the integration of engineering and technical education with science and production.

Engineering education and manufacturing integration is a dynamic multi-component system. Each state of the system corresponds to certain connections between its components, which represent one or another form of integration.

In the conditions of integration of education, science and production, it is necessary to provide a network educational-methodical system with a model adapted to market requirements, which ensures training of modern engineers and independent education.

A number of steps have been taken to develop the integration of science, education and production at the Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction named after Mirzo Ulugbek. As a specialist department, more than 10 higher educational and scientific research institutions, as well as 20 equipped with the most modern technologies, in order to train specialists in the educational direction "Technology of production of construction materials, products and structures" and to conduct scientific research on the creation of new types of construction materials close cooperation was established within the framework of "Integration of Science, Education and

Production Enterprises" with enterprises producing construction materials.

Students of our university's "Production of construction materials, products and constructions" educational direction are being organized in these enterprises not only for their professional internships, but also for graduation diploma work and master's research work in production enterprises equipped with modern technologies. One of such main partners is "KARSHI CONCH CEMENT", "TASHKENT CONCH CEMENT" and "ANDIJON CONCH CEMENT" enterprises of "Anhui Conch Cement Company Limited" of the People's Republic of China in Uzbekistan (pic. 1).

"Integration of science, education and production" is the joint use of the existing capabilities of the parties for mutual benefit.

Pic. 1. Science-education-production integration

In the academic year 2021-2022, 21 graduates and 4 graduate students of this field of education were hired at the factory after qualifying practice at the "Karshi-Conch" cement plant, defending their diplomas and master's theses, and are currently working in various positions.

In the 2022-2023 academic year, based on the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 8, 2022 No. PQ-416 "On measures to further improve the personnel training system in the field of architecture and construction", after our institute received the status of a university, paragraph 9 of Appendix 2 of this decision, paragraph 3- points 1-2-3 of clause 18, clause 19, clause 2-3 and 4 of clause 32 and 2 professors of the department "Technology of construction materials, products and constructions" to ensure the implementation of internships of professors and teachers in modern equipped foreign enterprises - teachers, also, 20 students of the 4th year of the "Production of construction materials, products and constructions" were sent to the foreign enterprises "KARSHI CONCH CEMENT" and TASHKENT CONCH CEMENT for a one-month internship and "training for a special profession". Since 2019, continuous monitoring of graduates employed in these cement factories has been carried out. The management and specialists of the enterprise gave good conclusions,

and it is noted that their professional competences are increasing year by year. The department has studied the personnel requirements of several cement plants until 2025, and the annual demand for only "engineer-technologists" in the cement plants of the Chinese company "Anhui Conch Cement Company Limited" is 60 to 80 people. Based on this request, based on the

proposal of the above enterprises, it was agreed to train specialists for the enterprises of the Republic of China operating in Uzbekistan for the production of building materials in cooperation with the Nanjing Polytechnic Polytechnic Institute of the People's Republic of China and the Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction (Pic. 2).

Pic. 2. Integration of production and education in the example of Karshi-Conch

In addition, based on the relevant clauses of the cooperation agreement between the Chinese foreign company "HENGYUAN CEMENT" and the university, a group of students studying in the field of "Manufacturing of construction materials, products and structures" will spend two months from April 1 to May 31, 2023 in the city of Cyril, Kyzyl Horda region of the Republic of Kazakhstan. After passing special educational practical courses on "physical-chemical analysis and quality control" at the center of special vocational education and training of the Chinese state and successfully defending diplomas, they are currently working as engineers-technologists at this plant.

More than 60 of our graduates work in cement production plants built and operated by Chinese partners in Uzbekistan.

In the academic year 2023-2024, together with the Nanjing Polytechnic Institute of the People's Republic of China and the Chinese cement plants operating in our country, work is being carried out to implement the essence of the concept of "Science, Education and Production".

In collaboration with Samarkand State Architecture and Construction University, Nanjing Polytechnic Institute and three cement plants belonging to Anhui Conch Cement Company Limited, it was mutually agreed to establish a "Training and Research Center" at the base of the "KARSHI CONCH CEMENT" plant

Pic. 3. Activities of the Center for Integration in Cooperation

It is envisaged that this Center will start its activities in full from the 2025-2026 academic year. The 2+2 project is also envisaged in this cooperation. The personnel trained in this center will be fully covered by the Chinese cement factories operating in Uzbekistan, and the results of the conducted scientific research are expected to be applied in these factories as well (pic. 3).

Starting from 2023, our university is establishing cooperation with the leading cement production company "Ackerman" in Russia.

Currently, the university is preparing proposals for the establishment of close mutually beneficial cooperation with the Akhangoron cement plant of the Russian company Akkerman.

Obstacles and challenges:

- the lack of adaptability of the educational (curriculum) program, curriculum and lesson schedules based on the demand for production specialists (branches of the department) and the presence of elements of the bureaucracy of the educational system;

- the presence of differences between the level of preparation of graduates of the educational institution and the requirements for the quality of personnel of production;

- many students have a responsible attitude to the educational process and the lack of a deep logical connection to work on further professional activities (the goal is only to get a diploma);

- due to rapidly developing technologies, it is difficult to reach higher education;

- old and poorly equipped scientific research base of higher education institutions;

- the fact that the base of existing scientific laboratories is not accredited and certified and the necessary funds are not allocated;

- poor functioning of the system of transfer of developments and discoveries made by scientists to production;

- underestimation of the role of production in the educational system.

Summary.

- training of a modern engineer based on the systematic integration of education, science and production is not only a scientific problem, but also one of the main directions of state policy;

- the integration of education, science and production is the structure of the national innovative system;

- if cooperation in the integration of education, science and production is not based on the principles of compatibility of interested parties, this cooperation will remain superficial and the intended goals cannot be achieved;

- this integration theoretically creates opportunities for scientists to implement their ideas in the form of finished products, for students to receive better education and for universities to see income from promising, high-tech venture investments.

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